

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

EBT Evaluation Report

(peer-review round 2)

for **TEBT-2023-0011**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Cross-mapping of terms used in chemical risk assessment with those used in systematic review: research protocol
Submission Reference	TEBT-2023-0011
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin, ORCID 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Primary Study Protocol
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.10965795
Status	In Peer-Review
Evaluation Date	4 June 2024
Evaluation Round	Peer review round 2
Recommendation	Revise
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	Authors have responded adequately to all comments, however some of their response to reviewers were not translated into amendments to the manuscript. Although these are documented through the open peer review process, it would be valuable to add these clarifications to the manuscript itself.

Editor's summary of Reviewers' Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from peer-reviewers' comments

This manuscript describes a protocol for cross-mapping core terms used by the systematic review and chemical risk assessment communities to improve inter-operability and communication. The first round of peer review generated very valuable and detailed comments on the proposed methodology that highlight where detail on specific steps and/or justification for the selection of a specific approach is lacking, including grounding the protocol on a solid up-to-date understanding of methods for consensus building and controlled vocabulary development. Some more fundamental questions were raised about the symmetry of the translation effort and the reciprocity of the exchange between the two communities.

The authors have clearly engaged with the peer review process and reflected on their proposed methods. The authors piloted the originally proposed Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) method on the document collections. As it did not perform as expected, a new and simpler manual approach has been suggested. As a result, the proposed methods have been amended and simplified.

The authors have also provided detailed answers to comments and in most instances have amended the manuscript accordingly. There are a few issues that have been addressed in responses to reviewers for which it would be desirable to also amend the text. This would improve transparency and therefore the quality of the planned research.

Seriousness of remaining issues identified with planned methods	There are no remaining serious issues with the planned methods. Minor revisions to the text are required to reflect clarifications offered as responses to reviewers' comments in the manuscript itself.
Potential additional work to overcome remaining issues	Very minimal. Only short clarifications are required.
Acceptability of characterising remaining limitations instead of planning additional work	The above short clarifications will effectively help explicitly state and characterise limitations recognised in responses to reviewers' comments.

Reviewers' comments

Reviewer comments are lightly edited and aggregated into the structure below by the Handling Editor

General comments

1. I very much like the new, sleeker methods.

Remaining issues that could materially impact the scientific quality of the planned research

2. I am pleased to read that discussions will be supported by an experienced and neutral moderator. I remain disappointed that reliable methods for consensus development (rather than only voting) are not clearly explained in the paper especially as there is a mature literature to draw on.
3. Lines 155-156: other sources might be used... will you search? Brainstorm among members? Clarification would be helpful.

Other remaining issues with the planned methods

4. We understand that the ethics of collecting race or ethnicity information about study participants are interpreted differently in different countries. You should explain the rules regarding collecting such information in the institution applying for ethical clearance in the manuscript to justify this omission.
5. The clarification offered as response to reviewers' comments is welcome. For transparency on this aspect of the methods, the content of the following paragraph ought to be added to the manuscript "The use of an experienced and neutral moderator should reduce the potential for some persons to dominate the discussion. Voting online after the event should also allow for more ease at disagreeing with 'strong personalities/ assumed higher in the hierarchical system. Also, we are planning for a diverse mix of experiences and backgrounds in the group. The plan is for the discussions to be facilitated by an experienced moderator (PW) who will be aware of the need to ensure dominant personalities do not overwhelm the discussion. The key element of the method is the asynchronous anonymous comment and voting. Because we are aiming at near-full consensus, this will give all participants the opportunity to contribute, with the requirement that their comments are taken into account. If the participants feel their comments are not responded to, they can vote "no" in the next round of voting." Followed by a brief statement regarding the limitations of the proposed approach. The citation provided in the response should also be included in the paper itself.

6. Lines 124-128: New information, “the TF-IDF” method was “not successful” – maybe say why so other people can understand for future projects of a similar nature.
7. The GRADE ontology mentioned by the authors in their response is not explained or cited in the manuscript.

Other questions and comments about the protocol

8. The abstract needs to be updated that CRA and SR definitions aren't authoritative. It's updated in lines 50-66, but the one on the cover page (in the system?) has not been, if that matters.
9. Reviewer 4, 4.1 Line 228-229. Pg 12 of review. Networks of members in the groups for recruitment – I still think it's important. Only recruiting people you know will not result in a diverse group. I am glad to see the text included in S-8.
10. “Is table S-1 a duplicate of table 1 (now table 2)” The clarification is helpful but I think it would be good to add that information in the caption for Table 2 (more detailed steps available in S-1).
11. The authors have made clear that their inspection of the core terminology will be limited to systematic reviews that include quantitative health outcomes, I can see that they are making a fair comparison. However, line 103 states that ‘For CRAs, the scope is limited to methods for quantitative systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence synthesis.’ My understanding is that for both CRAs and systematic reviews ‘the scope is limited to methods for quantitative systematic review of health effects of interventions and exposures and methods for evidence synthesis.’ I would like to see this same clarity reflected in the title. Without amending the title the asymmetry in scope remains as systematic reviews can include qualitative research, which is not of interest here.